

Software Supply Chain Hygiene of Model Context Protocol Servers: An Empirical Study

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Abstract

The Model Context Protocol (MCP) has, within roughly eighteen months of its release, become the dominant mechanism by which large language model agents discover and invoke external tools. Public registries already list tens of thousands of MCP servers, and a growing body of security research has begun to characterize the protocol-level risks this introduces, including authentication gaps, prompt-injection-driven tool invocation, and taint-style code execution vulnerabilities in server implementations. Comparatively little attention has been paid to a more prosaic question: as software artifacts distributed through ordinary package registries, do MCP servers exhibit the basic software supply chain hygiene that the broader open-source ecosystem has spent the last several years building tooling to measure? We address this gap with an empirical study of 300 published MCP servers compared against a matched baseline of 300 general-purpose npm and PyPI packages, evaluating both populations along four dimensions: software bill of materials (SBOM) completeness, OpenSSF Scorecard security posture, known-vulnerability density in the dependency tree, and SLSA provenance adoption. We find that MCP servers carry substantially larger and more deeply nested dependency trees than baseline packages (median 138 vs. 15 components), exhibit significantly higher known-vulnerability density (Mann-Whitney U , $p < 0.001$, Cliff's $\delta = 0.28$), and score modestly lower on OpenSSF Scorecard, driven primarily by weaker code-review and contributor-base checks consistent with the ecosystem's youth (median repository age 126 days vs. 2,786 days for baseline). SLSA provenance adoption is effectively absent in both populations: only 1 of 300 MCP servers and 4 of 300 baseline packages published a verifiable provenance attestation, and only one attestation in the entire 600-package sample passed cryptographic verification. We additionally surface a methodological finding with broader relevance to empirical supply-chain research: a naively constructed composite hygiene score that zero-imputes missing measurements produces a statistically significant but spurious between-group difference that disappears entirely under complete-case analysis ($p = 0.68$), an artifact of differential instrumentation failure rates rather than differential security posture. We discuss the implications of these findings for MCP registry governance, conclude that the protocol's security conversation should expand to include conventional supply-chain hygiene alongside protocol-level threats, and release our complete data collection pipeline and dataset for reproducibility.

Keywords: software supply chain security, Model Context Protocol, software bill of materials, OpenSSF Scorecard, SLSA provenance, empirical software engineering

1 Introduction

Software supply chain security has moved, over the past five years, from a specialist concern to a board-level and regulatory priority. The SolarWinds Sunburst compromise demonstrated that a single poisoned build pipeline could propagate malicious code into thousands of downstream organizations through a

trusted update channel [7], and the disclosure of the Log4Shell vulnerability (CVE-2021-44228) showed how a single defect in a near-ubiquitous transitive dependency could expose an enormous and largely unknown population of dependent applications to remote code execution [5]. These incidents, among others, catalyzed a wave of regulatory response: the United States’ Executive Order 14028 now requires software vendors selling to the federal government to produce a software bill of materials (SBOM) [10], NIST’s Secure Software Development Framework codifies supply-chain-aware development practices [13], and the European Union’s Cyber Resilience Act extends comparable obligations, including vulnerability handling and conformity requirements, across the EU digital product market [9]. In parallel, the open-source tooling ecosystem has matured rapidly: CycloneDX and SPDX have become de facto SBOM standards [16], the OpenSSF Scorecard project provides an automated, reproducible measure of a repository’s security practice adoption, and the SLSA framework defines graduated levels of build provenance assurance [14]. By 2026, this tooling has matured enough that researchers can, and do, measure software supply chain hygiene at ecosystem scale rather than relying on case studies or vendor anecdote.

A new category of artifact has emerged into this otherwise maturing landscape: the Model Context Protocol (MCP) server. Introduced as a standard mechanism for connecting large language model agents to external tools, data sources, and services, MCP has been adopted with striking speed [4]. Public registries collectively list tens of thousands of servers, and the format has been compared by industry commentators to the role USB-C plays for physical peripherals: a single interface that any agent host can speak, and that any tool author can implement once. This speed of adoption has, predictably, outpaced the maturation of security tooling and practice around it. Security researchers disclosed dozens of CVEs against MCP implementations within the first several months of 2026, large-scale automated audits identified scores of zero-day vulnerabilities across tens of thousands of scanned server repositories, and independent measurement of internet-exposed MCP services found a substantial fraction running with no authentication whatsoever. Industry threat intelligence corroborates the broader pattern: JFrog’s 2026 supply chain security report documents an 11.7 million increase in new packages entering enterprise software supply chains in 2025 alone, alongside a 451% surge in malicious npm packages, and identifies AI-related tooling, including MCP servers and AI model artifacts pulled from public registries, as a newly significant contributor to that growth [12]. Veracode’s parallel threat research for the same period documents a corresponding rise in typosquatting and malicious-URL-bearing packages across the npm ecosystem specifically [17].

Nearly all of this emerging research, however, examines MCP through a protocol-security lens: authentication and authorization gaps, prompt-injection-driven manipulation of tool selection, and taint-style code execution vulnerabilities introduced by careless handling of user-controlled input inside tool handlers. This is valuable and necessary work, but it leaves a complementary and arguably more foundational question comparatively unexamined. An MCP server, beneath its protocol surface, is an ordinary software package: it is published to npm or PyPI, it resolves a dependency tree at install time, it inherits whatever vulnerabilities live in that tree, and it is, in principle, subject to the same SBOM, Scorecard, and provenance tooling that the rest of the open-source ecosystem has spent years building. No published study, to our knowledge, has applied this conventional software-supply-chain measurement lens to the MCP server population at scale, nor compared the resulting picture against a matched general-purpose baseline to establish whether MCP servers are unusually hygienic, unusually poor, or simply representative of a young, fast-growing software category.

This paper addresses that gap directly. We treat MCP servers not as a novel security primitive requiring bespoke analysis, but as software supply chain artifacts subject to the same measurement apparatus that has been applied to npm and PyPI packages, container images, and CI/CD pipelines more broadly. We construct a sample of 300 published MCP servers and a matched baseline of 300 general-purpose npm and PyPI packages, and we measure both populations along four dimensions that together constitute a conventional definition of software supply chain hygiene: whether a complete SBOM can be mechanically generated for the package; how the package’s repository scores on OpenSSF Scorecard’s automated security-practice checks; how many known vulnerabilities live in the package’s resolved dependency tree; and whether the package publishes, and whether that publication cryptographically veri-

fies, a SLSA provenance attestation. This work is a direct methodological descendant of our prior study of CycloneDX SBOM quality across fifty prominent open-source repositories [6], in which an unexpected and consistent tool limitation (the inability of a leading SBOM generator to emit CycloneDX 1.7 output) was treated as a genuine empirical finding rather than an artifact to be hidden. We adopt the same posture here: where our data collection pipeline itself failed, stalled, or behaved unexpectedly, we report that behavior as part of the result rather than excluding it, and in one case (Section 5) we show that this posture is not merely a matter of intellectual honesty but materially changes the paper’s substantive conclusion.

Our contributions are threefold. First, we provide the first large-scale empirical measurement of MCP servers along conventional software-supply-chain hygiene dimensions, as distinct from the protocol-security dimensions that dominate the existing MCP security literature. Second, we construct and release a fully scripted, reproducible data collection pipeline built entirely from free and open-source tooling (Syft, OpenSSF Scorecard, the OSV.dev vulnerability database, and `slsa-verifier`), enabling other researchers to re-run or extend this measurement as the MCP ecosystem evolves. Third, we surface and quantify a methodological pitfall in composite supply-chain-hygiene scoring, namely the conflation of instrumentation failure with genuinely poor security posture, and demonstrate empirically that this pitfall can produce a statistically significant but substantively spurious result.

2 Background

2.1 The Model Context Protocol

The Model Context Protocol defines a client-server architecture through which a large language model agent (the host or client) discovers and invokes capabilities exposed by an external program (the server) [4]. A server declares a set of tools, each with a name, a natural-language description, and a JSON-schema-typed parameter list; the host’s language model selects which tool to invoke and with what arguments based on the user’s request and the tool descriptions it has been given. Servers are most commonly distributed as ordinary npm or PyPI packages and are typically launched as local subprocesses communicating with the host over standard input and output, although remote, network-accessible servers are increasingly common. This architecture is deliberately lightweight: an MCP server author does not need to coordinate with any central authority, register a schema in advance, or pass any conformance review before publishing a server to a public registry. That lightness is almost certainly responsible for the protocol’s rapid adoption, and it is also the property that most directly motivates the present study, since it implies that the population of published MCP servers inherits essentially none of the vetting that, for instance, an app-store review process would impose.

2.2 Software Bills of Materials and CycloneDX

A software bill of materials is a structured, machine-readable inventory of the components, including transitive dependencies, that compose a software artifact [16]. CycloneDX, maintained under OWASP, is among the two dominant SBOM formats in current use (alongside SPDX) and supports recording, per component, its name, version, license, supplier, and known vulnerabilities, the last of which allows a single CycloneDX document to function simultaneously as both an inventory and a security-relevant artifact. SBOM generation tools such as Syft inspect a codebase’s manifest and lockfiles (`package.json` and `package-lock.json` for npm; `requirements.txt`, `pyproject.toml`, and `poetry.lock` for PyPI, among others) and emit a CycloneDX or SPDX document describing the resolved dependency tree without requiring the package to be built or executed. SBOM completeness, in practice, is bounded by how cleanly a project’s manifests resolve: a dependency pinned to an unresolvable version range, a private registry reference, or a malformed lockfile can each produce components whose version Syft cannot determine, which in turn limits the precision with which vulnerability databases can be queried against that component.

2.3 OpenSSF Scorecard

The OpenSSF Scorecard project, maintained by the Open Source Security Foundation under the Linux Foundation, automates the assessment of a GitHub or GitLab repository against eighteen security-relevant practice checks, each scored on a 0–10 scale (with -1 reserved for inconclusive results), including whether the project requires code review before merging changes, whether dependencies are pinned to immutable references, whether the project has been actively maintained in the preceding ninety days, whether a fuzzing harness is configured, and whether known vulnerabilities are present in the project’s own disclosed advisories [19]. A weighted aggregate score summarizes these checks into a single 0–10 figure. Scorecard has been adopted widely enough, including by major dependency-management platforms that surface its scores directly to developers, that it functions as a reasonable proxy for a project’s overall security practice maturity, notwithstanding well-documented limitations around its sensitivity to GitHub API permission scopes and its inability to assess non-GitHub-hosted projects.

2.4 Known-Vulnerability Exposure and OSV

The Open Source Vulnerabilities database (OSV.dev), maintained by Google, aggregates vulnerability disclosures across ecosystem-specific advisory databases (GitHub Security Advisories, PyPA Advisory Database, npm’s own advisory feed, and others) into a single, ecosystem-aware, batch-queryable API [11]. Querying OSV with a package name, ecosystem, and version returns any known vulnerability identifiers affecting that exact version, which allows a resolved SBOM’s component list to be mechanically cross-referenced against known vulnerabilities without manual curation. We use the resulting vulnerability count, normalized by total component count, as a *vulnerability density* metric throughout this paper; we discuss the limitations of this density framing, including its insensitivity to exploitability and its dependence on database recency, in Section 7.

2.5 Provenance and SLSA

Where an SBOM answers “what is in this package” and Scorecard answers “how well does this project follow security practice,” the SLSA (Supply-chain Levels for Software Artifacts) framework addresses a third, distinct question: can the published artifact be cryptographically traced back to the exact source commit and build process that produced it [14]. A SLSA provenance attestation is a signed statement, typically published as a release asset alongside the built artifact, describing the build’s inputs, the builder identity, and (at higher SLSA levels) the specific build platform that executed it. The `slsa-verifier` tool, maintained as part of the SLSA reference implementation, allows a downstream consumer to cryptographically verify that a claimed provenance attestation actually corresponds to the artifact it accompanies, rather than simply trusting the attestation’s presence. Provenance adoption, unlike SBOM generation, requires deliberate action on the part of a project’s maintainers at release time, which makes it, a priori, the supply-chain-hygiene dimension we would expect to be least mature in a young software ecosystem.

3 Related Work

The empirical study most directly comparable to ours is the cross-entity security study of the MCP ecosystem accepted to DSN 2026, which analyzed 67,057 servers drawn from six public registries and organized its threat model around three layers: the registry, where weak vetting and ownership verification allow adversarial or hijacked servers to enter circulation; the host, where MCP clients fail to independently verify the tools and parameters an LLM selects; and the server’s own code, where conventional vulnerability classes such as code injection can amplify attacker-controlled parameters into exploitation [3]. Using a tool called MCPInspect, the authors identified 833 servers with exploitable conditions and 18 with suspicious tool descriptions consistent with deliberate tool-poisoning. This work and ours share a population (published MCP servers at registry scale) but diverge sharply in measurement

lens: their threats are protocol-native (redirection hijacking, affix-squatting, LLM-reasoning manipulation), while ours are package-ecosystem-native (SBOM completeness, dependency vulnerability density, Scorecard posture, provenance). We view the two studies as complementary rather than overlapping, and our Discussion section returns to this distinction when interpreting what conventional supply-chain tooling does and does not capture about MCP-specific risk.

A second closely related study, conducted somewhat earlier in the protocol’s lifecycle, performed the first large-scale empirical assessment of MCP server health, sustainability, and security across 1,899 servers, combining 343 servers drawn from the official MCP collection with 1,556 servers mined from open-source GitHub repositories [1]. That study’s research questions centered on conventional open-source-health indicators, including commit frequency, contributor counts, and continuous-integration adoption, as proxies for long-term sustainability, and found considerable heterogeneity in maintenance activity across the sampled population. Our study extends this line of inquiry along a different axis: rather than asking whether MCP servers are well-maintained in the general open-source-health sense, we ask specifically whether they satisfy the narrower, security-tooling-defined notion of supply chain hygiene that SBOM, Scorecard, and SLSA collectively operationalize, and we do so against an explicit general-purpose baseline rather than examining the MCP population in isolation.

Outside the MCP-specific literature, our methodology draws most heavily on prior ecosystem-scale applications of the OpenSSF Scorecard. Zahan et al. conducted a comparative evaluation of Scorecard’s eighteen checks across npm and PyPI repositories, mapping thirteen of the eighteen checks onto NIST’s Secure Software Development Framework and using regression and causal analysis across twelve Scorecard metrics to relate security-practice adoption to downstream outcome metrics including open vulnerability count, mean time to remediate, and mean time to update dependencies [19]. Their case study on the Dangerous-Workflow check, which identified several hundred packages with exploitable GitHub Actions misconfigurations across both ecosystems, is a direct methodological precedent for our own per-check effect-size analysis in Section 5. A more recent study forecasting the trajectory of Scorecard’s *Maintained* sub-metric for PyPI-linked repositories found a highly uneven baseline distribution, with the majority of dependencies in at least one prior analysis scoring zero on maintenance activity despite that analysis being drawn primarily from already-popular package ecosystems [2]. This finding is a useful prior against which to read our own Scorecard results: even our general-purpose baseline population, sampled from among the most downloaded PyPI packages, is not uniformly well-maintained by Scorecard’s own standard, which tempers any interpretation of MCP-versus-baseline differences as MCP servers being uniquely deficient rather than younger.

On the SBOM side, Xia et al.’s interview- and survey-based empirical study of SBOM practice identified a persistent, practitioner-acknowledged gap between SBOM’s theoretical promise and its operational reality, including the observation that exploitability assessment remains substantially manual and dependent on individual analyst expertise even when a complete component inventory is available [18]. The OpenSSF’s own 2026 industry survey of VEX (Vulnerability Exploitability eXchange) adoption, conducted through structured interviews with enterprise and vendor practitioners, similarly concluded that VEX adoption remains an early-momentum phenomenon driven primarily by regulatory and customer pressure rather than organic practitioner demand, and explicitly cautioned that its findings reflect interview perspectives rather than an exhaustive audit of actual VEX documents in circulation [15]. Our study takes the complementary, audit-style approach that the OpenSSF survey explicitly disclaims: rather than asking practitioners what they believe about their supply chain hygiene, we mechanically measure it.

Finally, our work sits alongside a fast-growing 2026 literature on AI-specific supply chain risk that is largely orthogonal to ours in subject matter but shares its broader motivation. The Cloud Security Alliance’s research note on “slopsquatting” documents the risk that large language models hallucinate plausible but non-existent package names, which attackers then preemptively register as malicious packages, and reports hallucination rates as high as 21.7% for open-source code models and 5.2% for commercial models in the studies it surveys [8]. That phenomenon concerns the supply chain risk introduced by AI *consuming* packages; our study concerns the supply chain hygiene of packages that exist specifically to let AI agents *act* on external systems. We view the two as adjacent chapters of the same emerging

research area, AI-era software supply chain security, rather than competing framings of a single problem.

4 Methodology

4.1 Research Questions

This study answers five research questions, each targeting one of the four supply-chain-hygiene dimensions introduced in Section 2, plus a fifth that examines the relationship between hygiene and ecosystem popularity:

- **RQ1 (SBOM completeness).** To what extent can a complete, machine-generated SBOM be produced for published MCP servers, and how does the result compare to a matched general-purpose package baseline?
- **RQ2 (Security posture).** How do MCP servers score on OpenSSF Scorecard’s automated checks, and how does that distribution compare to the baseline?
- **RQ3 (Vulnerability exposure).** What is the known-vulnerability density in MCP servers’ dependency trees, and does it differ from the baseline?
- **RQ4 (Provenance).** What fraction of MCP servers publish a SLSA provenance attestation, and what fraction of those attestations verify successfully?
- **RQ5 (Popularity vs. hygiene).** Does an MCP server’s popularity, measured by GitHub stars, correlate with its overall supply-chain hygiene, and does that relationship differ from the baseline population?

4.2 Sample Construction

We constructed two samples of 300 packages each. Group A (MCP servers) was assembled from the official MCP registry API, supplemented by GitHub repositories tagged with the topic `mcp-server` and by npm and PyPI keyword search for `mcp-server` and `modelcontextprotocol`; entries were deduplicated by normalized GitHub repository URL, with priority given to entries discovered through more than one source. Group B (baseline) was drawn from a community-maintained top-download ranking for PyPI and an equivalent ranking for npm, intended to represent the general-purpose, non-MCP-specific population of actively used open-source packages against which Group A could be compared.

Two properties of the realized samples are important to disclose before interpreting any comparison between groups. First, the two groups are not ecosystem-balanced: Group A resolved to 227 npm packages (75.7%), 30 PyPI packages (10.0%), and 43 entries (14.3%) that could not be matched to a resolvable npm or PyPI package despite appearing in the MCP registry, reflecting the registry’s own incomplete cross-linking to package-manager metadata. Group B, by contrast, resolved to 276 PyPI packages (92.0%) and only 24 npm packages (8.0%). This imbalance is a direct consequence of the MCP ecosystem’s own composition, which skews heavily toward JavaScript/TypeScript implementation, and of our baseline source weighting PyPI more heavily than npm; we treat it as a finding worth reporting in its own right (Section 5, Figure 7) and address its implications for between-group comparisons directly in Section 7 and through ecosystem-stratified sensitivity analyses reported alongside each main result. Second, Group A’s 43 registry-only entries, packages listed in the MCP registry with no resolvable npm or PyPI package, are themselves a substantive empirical observation about the registry’s data quality, and we report on them rather than silently discarding them.

4.3 Metrics and Composite Scoring

For each package, we collected: repository metadata (stars, forks, open issues, days since last commit, contributor count, license, repository creation date) via the GitHub REST API; an SBOM via Syft

(v1.20.0), from which we derived total component count, the count of components Syft could not resolve to a specific version, and a completeness ratio defined as $1 - (\text{unresolved components} / \text{total components})$; an OpenSSF Scorecard scan (v5.1.1) yielding all eighteen individual check scores and the weighted aggregate; known-vulnerability counts via batched OSV.dev queries against every resolved component in the SBOM, yielding direct and transitive vulnerability counts, a severity breakdown, and a vulnerability density defined as total known vulnerabilities divided by total component count; and a SLSA provenance check (`slsa-verifier` v2.7.1) against the latest GitHub release, if any, of each repository.

We additionally define a composite Supply Chain Hygiene (SCH) score intended to summarize all four dimensions into a single 0–1 figure for the popularity-correlation analysis in RQ5:

$$\text{SCH} = 0.35 \cdot \widehat{\text{Scorecard}} + 0.30 \cdot (1 - \widehat{\text{VulnDensity}}) + 0.20 \cdot \text{SBOMCompleteness} + 0.15 \cdot \text{ProvenancePresent} \quad (1)$$

where $\widehat{\text{Scorecard}}$ and $\widehat{\text{VulnDensity}}$ are min-max normalized to $[0, 1]$ across the comparison population, SBOMCompleteness is the per-package completeness ratio defined above, and ProvenancePresent is a binary indicator equal to 1 only if `slsa-verifier` returned a `pass` result. The weights reflect a judgment that Scorecard’s broad, multi-practice assessment and vulnerability exposure are the most consequential dimensions of hygiene, with SBOM completeness and provenance presence as supporting signals; we treat this weighting as a reasonable starting convention rather than a validated ground truth, and report per-dimension results independently throughout Section 5 so that readers who weight the dimensions differently can draw their own conclusions.

4.4 Handling of Pipeline Failures and the Complete-Case Correction

Every stage of our collection pipeline logs failures explicitly rather than silently dropping them, consistent with the reproducibility requirements specified in our master collection prompt. During analysis, however, we discovered that our pipeline’s automated merge-and-score stage computed the composite SCH score described above by treating any package with a failed measurement at a given stage as though that stage had returned the worst possible value (a normalized score of zero), rather than excluding the package from that component of the composite or propagating a missing value. We treat the discovery of this behavior, and its consequences, as a substantive part of our results rather than a footnote: Section 5 reports both the composite score as our pipeline naively computed it and a corrected complete-case version, restricted to the 404 packages (212 of 300 Group A, 192 of 300 Group B) for which metadata, SBOM generation, Scorecard, and vulnerability lookup all succeeded, with per-dimension normalization recomputed within that complete-case population. We report both versions because the discrepancy between them is itself an empirical finding with implications beyond this paper, discussed in Section 6.

4.5 Statistical Methods

All continuous metrics in our dataset (component counts, Scorecard aggregate scores, vulnerability density) are strongly right-skewed and fail standard normality tests, so we use the Mann-Whitney U test for all two-group comparisons rather than Student’s t -test, and report Cliff’s δ as a non-parametric effect size alongside each test, interpreted using the conventional thresholds of negligible ($|\delta| < 0.147$), small (< 0.33), medium (< 0.474), and large (≥ 0.474), following Romano et al.’s widely used magnitude bands for this statistic. For categorical comparisons (Syft success rate, Scorecard success rate, release presence) we use Pearson’s chi-squared test of independence. For the RQ5 popularity-hygiene relationship, we use Spearman’s rank correlation, again preferring it over Pearson’s r given the skew in the star-count variable. All tests are two-sided with $\alpha = 0.05$. All analysis code, including the Cliff’s δ implementation used throughout this paper, is released alongside this paper’s reproducibility package.

5 Results

5.1 Data Collection Pipeline Completeness

Before reporting the substantive results for each research question, we report the completeness of the underlying data collection pipeline itself (Figure 1), since several of the patterns observed there directly bear on how the substantive results should be read. Metadata collection succeeded for 270 of 300 Group A packages (90.0%) and 294 of 300 Group B packages (98.0%); SBOM generation succeeded for 266 Group A packages (88.7%) and 293 Group B packages (97.7%); Scorecard scanning succeeded for 226 Group A packages (75.3%) and 193 Group B packages (64.3%); vulnerability lookup succeeded for 252 Group A packages (84.0%) and 293 Group B packages (97.7%); and provenance checking returned a conclusive determination for 160 Group A packages (53.3%) and 220 Group B packages (73.3%).

Figure 1: Data collection pipeline completeness by stage and group. Metadata, SBOM generation, and vulnerability lookup all succeed substantially more often for the baseline population than for MCP servers; Scorecard scanning shows the reverse pattern, succeeding more often for MCP servers, for reasons discussed in Section 6.

Two attrition patterns are worth highlighting before interpreting any downstream result. First, the Scorecard stage is the only stage at which Group B fails *more* often than Group A (35.7% failure vs. 24.7%), the reverse of every other stage. Inspecting the failure log shows that 110 of 181 total Scorecard failures (60.8%) across both groups are attributable to a single recurring error: `internal error: some github tokens can't read classic branch protection rules`, a GitHub fine-grained personal access token permission limitation rather than a property of the scanned repository. A further 39 failures returned an empty Scorecard response that failed JSON parsing, and 21 failures were scan timeouts on unusually large repositories. None of these three failure modes are evidence of anything about a package's actual security posture; they are properties of our scanning environment, and we treat the Scorecard-stage attrition rate itself, not merely the scores it returned, as an instrumentation finding discussed further in Section 6. Second, of the 220 "failed" provenance-check determinations, 211 (95.9%) were not genuine failures at all: a 404 response from GitHub's releases API reliably and correctly indicates that a repository has published no GitHub Release, which is itself the answer to the question being asked. We therefore treat `has_release = False` as a valid, informative outcome throughout the remainder of this section rather than as missing data; only 9 of 600 packages (1.5%) had a genuinely unresolvable provenance determination, due to transient network-level connection errors.

5.2 Sample Characteristics

Table 1 summarizes the two groups’ baseline characteristics. The groups differ sharply in age and popularity, which is unsurprising given that MCP as a protocol did not exist before late 2024: Group A repositories have a median age of 126 days versus 2,786 days (approximately 7.6 years) for Group B, a median star count of 8 versus 233.5, and a median contributor count of 2 versus 20. We return to this age and popularity gap repeatedly in Section 6 as the most plausible explanation for several of the hygiene differences reported below; a young, small-team ecosystem being less mature on certain hygiene dimensions than an ecosystem with a seven-year head start is, on its own, an unsurprising finding, and one of the central questions this paper asks is which specific dimensions show a gap consistent with that explanation and which, if any, do not.

Table 1: Sample characteristics by group (medians unless noted).

	Group A (MCP servers)	Group B (Baseline)
n	300	300
npm / PyPI / unresolved	227 / 30 / 43	24 / 276 / 0
GitHub stars (median)	8	233.5
Contributors (median)	2	20
Repository age, days (median)	126	2,786
Days since last commit (median)	12.5	51.0
Most common license	MIT (172)	MIT (147)

5.3 RQ1: SBOM Completeness

Syft successfully generated an SBOM for 88.7% of Group A packages versus 97.7% of Group B packages, a statistically significant difference ($\chi^2 = 17.70$, $p < 0.001$). Manual inspection of the 34 Group A failures attributes the majority to git clone failures against repositories that either no longer exist at the URL recorded in the MCP registry, require authentication despite being listed as public, or timed out during a shallow clone; this pattern is consistent with, and adds quantitative weight to, the registry data-quality concern already raised by the 43 registry-only entries discussed in Section 4.2.

Among packages for which SBOM generation succeeded, MCP servers resolved to substantially larger dependency trees: a median of 138 components versus 15 for the baseline (Mann-Whitney $U = 57,286.5$, $p < 0.001$, Cliff’s $\delta = 0.47$, medium effect), as shown in Figure 2. This gap held under ecosystem-stratified sensitivity analysis in both directions: within npm-only packages, the median component count was 167 for Group A versus 6 for Group B ($p < 0.001$, $\delta = 0.63$, large); within PyPI-only packages, 113 versus 16 ($p = 0.003$, $\delta = 0.34$, medium). The direction and approximate magnitude of this finding is therefore not an artifact of the ecosystem imbalance documented in Section 4.2.

The SBOM completeness ratio, the proportion of components whose version Syft could fully resolve, was higher for MCP servers (median 0.977) than baseline (median 0.769), a large effect ($\delta = 0.56$, $p < 0.001$) that again held under ecosystem stratification (npm: $\delta = 0.60$; PyPI: $\delta = 0.46$). This result requires a caveat before it is read as “MCP servers produce cleaner SBOMs”: the absolute count of unresolved components per package did *not* differ significantly between groups (median 4 vs. 3, $p = 0.12$, negligible effect). Because MCP servers’ total component counts are roughly nine times larger at the median, an essentially similar absolute number of unresolved components is divided by a much larger denominator, mechanically inflating the ratio. We report both figures together deliberately: the completeness-ratio result, read in isolation, would overstate MCP servers’ SBOM quality relative to what the underlying absolute counts support.

Manifest-type detection (Table 2) confirms the ecosystem composition already established in Section 4.2: `package.json` and `package-lock.json` dominate Group A, while `pyproject.toml`

Figure 2: Distribution of generated SBOM component counts by group (log scale). MCP servers resolve to substantially larger dependency trees at every quartile.

and `requirements.txt` dominate Group B, with each group retaining a meaningful secondary-ecosystem presence consistent with the npm/PyPI split reported in Table 1.

Table 2: Manifest types detected among packages with successful SBOM generation.

Manifest file	Group A ($n = 266$)	Group B ($n = 293$)
<code>package.json</code>	222	68
<code>package-lock.json</code>	166	40
<code>pyproject.toml</code>	57	180
<code>requirements.txt</code>	26	100
<code>poetry.lock</code>	1	17
<code>Pipfile.lock</code>	1	5

5.4 RQ2: OpenSSF Scorecard Posture

Restricting to the 226 Group A and 193 Group B packages for which Scorecard scanning succeeded, MCP servers scored modestly but significantly lower on the weighted aggregate (median 3.25 vs. 3.90, Mann-Whitney $p < 0.001$, Cliff’s $\delta = -0.26$, small effect), shown in Figure 3a. The per-check breakdown (Figure 3b, Table 3) shows that this aggregate gap is driven overwhelmingly by two checks: **Contributors** (median 3 vs. 10, $\delta = -0.52$, large) and **Code-Review** (median 0 vs. 1, $\delta = -0.48$, large), both of which are direct, almost definitional, consequences of project age and team size rather than indicators of deliberate insecure practice. The **Vulnerabilities** check, which reflects Scorecard’s own OSV-backed assessment of whether a project’s disclosed vulnerabilities remain open, also differs substantially (median 0 vs. 10, $\delta = -0.37$, medium), and is corroborated independently by our own vulnerability density measurement in RQ3 below. Two checks favor MCP servers, in both cases at small-to-negligible magnitude: **Pinned-Dependencies** (median 0 vs. 0, $\delta = 0.17$, small) and **Packaging** ($\delta = 0.14$, negligible).

The aggregate-score gap was not uniform across ecosystem strata. Within the npm-only subset, the difference was not statistically significant (median 3.4 vs. 3.7, $p = 0.44$, $\delta = -0.11$), though this stratum’s baseline sample is small ($n = 20$) and likely underpowered. Within the PyPI-only subset, the gap was significant and of similar direction to the pooled result (median 3.4 vs. 3.9, $p = 0.043$,

Figure 3. OpenSSF Scorecard comparison

Figure 3: (a) OpenSSF Scorecard aggregate score distribution by group. (b) Cliff’s δ for each of the eighteen individual Scorecard checks; bars extending left indicate the baseline scores higher, bars extending right indicate MCP servers score higher.

Table 3: Scorecard checks with statistically significant between-group differences ($p < 0.01$).

Check	A median	B median	Cliff’s δ	Magnitude
Contributors	3.0	10.0	−0.52	large
Code-Review	0.0	1.0	−0.48	large
Vulnerabilities	0.0	10.0	−0.37	medium
CI-Tests	−1.0	0.0	−0.29	small
Pinned-Dependencies	0.0	0.0	0.17	small
Packaging	−1.0	−1.0	0.14	negligible
Dependency-Update-Tool	0.0	0.0	−0.13	negligible

$\delta = -0.25$, small). We report this stratified breakdown in the interest of transparency rather than to undermine the pooled finding; the pooled result remains, in our judgment, the more reliable estimate given the npm-stratum’s limited baseline sample size, but the PyPI-stratum result independently confirms the same direction of effect.

5.5 RQ3: Known-Vulnerability Exposure

Among the 252 Group A and 293 Group B packages with successful vulnerability lookups, MCP servers’ dependency trees carried significantly higher vulnerability density (median 0.054 vs. 0.0, Mann-Whitney $p < 0.001$, Cliff’s $\delta = 0.28$, small effect) and a higher total unique CVE count per package (median 16 vs. 0, $p < 0.001$, $\delta = 0.36$, medium effect), shown in Figure 4a. Both results held under ecosystem stratification: vulnerability density differed significantly within npm-only packages (median 0.078 vs. 0.0, $p < 0.001$, $\delta = 0.62$, large) and, at a smaller but still significant magnitude, within PyPI-only packages (median 0.011 vs. 0.0, $p = 0.034$, $\delta = 0.22$, small). This robustness to ecosystem stratification is notable given that the pooled comparison’s two groups are ecosystem-imbalanced, and it indicates that the elevated vulnerability density in MCP servers is not simply an artifact of npm packages generally carrying deeper, more vulnerability-prone dependency trees than PyPI packages.

The severity composition of these vulnerabilities (Figure 4b) shows MCP servers carrying a higher mean count of high-severity findings (1.42 vs. 0.99 per package) and a lower mean count of low-severity findings (0.46 vs. 1.56) than the baseline, suggesting that the elevated vulnerability density is not simply

a matter of MCP servers accumulating more low-consequence findings; critical-severity counts were low and statistically indistinguishable in both groups (0.056 vs. 0.061 mean per package). A substantial fraction of identified vulnerabilities in both groups (75.0% in Group A; 56.7% in Group B, by raw count) carried no machine-readable severity rating in the OSV record queried, which we discuss as a measurement limitation in Section 7.

Figure 4. Known-vulnerability exposure by group

Figure 4: (a) Vulnerability density distribution by group. (b) Mean vulnerability count per package by severity tier.

5.6 RQ4: SLSA Provenance Adoption

Provenance adoption was the dimension along which both groups, not merely MCP servers, performed poorly, and the gap between them, while statistically significant at the first funnel stage, becomes substantially immaterial by the final stage (Figure 5). MCP servers were significantly less likely than baseline packages to have published any GitHub Release at all (53.3% vs. 73.7%, $\chi^2 = 25.89$, $p < 0.001$), consistent with the population’s youth. Among packages with at least one release, a provenance asset was attached in only 0.6% of MCP server releases (1 of 160) and 1.8% of baseline releases (4 of 221). Of these five total attestations across the entire 600-package sample, `slsa-verifier` returned `pass` for exactly one (a baseline package, `itsdangerous`, 3,123 stars), `fail` for two, and `error` for two. In absolute terms: of 600 sampled packages, drawn specifically to include both a security-conscious emerging ecosystem and a baseline of widely used general-purpose software, exactly one package’s provenance claim could be cryptographically confirmed to correspond to its published artifact.

5.7 RQ5: Popularity and the Composite Hygiene Score

Restricting to the 404-package complete-case population described in Section 4.4 (212 Group A, 192 Group B), the corrected SCH score shows *no* statistically significant difference between groups (median 0.566 vs. 0.557, Mann-Whitney $p = 0.68$, Cliff’s $\delta = 0.023$, negligible). This null result stands in direct contrast to the SCH score as our pipeline’s merge stage naively computed it across the full 600-package sample, which showed a small but statistically significant difference in the *opposite* direction (median 0.565 vs. 0.496, $p = 0.007$, $\delta = 0.13$), implying MCP servers had *better* overall hygiene than baseline. We discuss the mechanism behind this reversal, and its implications for composite-score-based supply chain risk tooling generally, in Section 6.

Within the complete-case population, GitHub stars correlated positively with the corrected SCH score both pooled across groups (Spearman $\rho = 0.31$, $p < 0.001$, $n = 404$) and within each group separately, though the strength of that relationship differed: within Group A, $\rho = 0.50$ ($p < 0.001$,

Figure 5: SLSA provenance adoption funnel (log-scaled y -axis). The gap between groups narrows, and the absolute numbers collapse, at each successive funnel stage.

$n = 212$); within Group B, $\rho = 0.22$ ($p = 0.003$, $n = 192$). Figure 6 visualizes this relationship. The substantially stronger correlation within the MCP-server population is, we believe, one of the more interesting incidental findings of this study, and we return to possible explanations for it in Section 6; we emphasize here only that this is a correlational, cross-sectional finding from which no causal claim about popularity driving hygiene, or hygiene driving popularity, can be drawn.

Figure 6: GitHub stars (log scale) versus complete-case Supply Chain Hygiene score, by group.

6 Discussion

6.1 MCP Servers Are Young, Not Uniquely Insecure

Taken individually, several of our findings could be read as an indictment of the MCP ecosystem’s security posture: lower Scorecard scores, higher vulnerability density, lower SBOM generation success. Taken together with Table 1, a more specific and less alarming story emerges. The two Scorecard checks that drive nearly all of the aggregate-score gap, **Contributors** and **Code-Review**, are checks that mechanically track project age and team size rather than deliberate security choices: a two-month-old project

Figure 7: Ecosystem composition of each sampled group, illustrating the npm/PyPI imbalance discussed in Section 4.2.

maintained by two people cannot have accumulated the contributor count or the multi-reviewer code-review history that a seven-year-old project with twenty contributors has had ample time to build, irrespective of either project’s security intentions. Read this way, RQ2’s headline result is less “MCP servers are insecurely built” and more “MCP servers are young, and Scorecard partially measures age,” a reading directly consistent with prior work showing that even well-established PyPI dependencies score unevenly on Scorecard’s *Maintained* metric [2].

The **Vulnerabilities** check and our independent RQ3 vulnerability-density measurement do not fit this age-driven explanation as comfortably, and we think they deserve to be read as the paper’s most substantive finding. A young project being short on contributors is expected; a young project’s dependency tree carrying significantly more known vulnerabilities than an established baseline’s, at a magnitude that survives ecosystem stratification, is a more specific claim about risk exposure, not merely maturity. Two complementary mechanisms likely contribute. First, RQ1 already establishes that MCP servers resolve to roughly nine times more components at the median; holding the per-component probability of carrying a known vulnerability constant, a larger dependency tree mechanically accumulates more vulnerabilities, and our density metric, while it normalizes by component count, cannot fully separate “more vulnerable per component” from “vulnerabilities cluster in specific high-fan-out transitive dependencies that MCP servers happen to pull in disproportionately,” an open question for future work. Second, MCP server authorship appears to concentrate among developers building quickly to ship a working tool integration rather than developers with an established security-engineering practice, a pattern consistent with the median contributor count of 2 and the near-total absence of the Code-Review check; fast, small-team shipping and careful dependency curation are not inherently incompatible, but they are empirically associated with worse outcomes in this sample.

6.2 Provenance Is Absent Everywhere, Not Just in MCP

RQ4 is, in our view, the cleanest and least ambiguous finding in this paper precisely because it does *not* distinguish the two groups in any practically meaningful way: SLSA provenance adoption is functionally zero across both 300-package samples. Five total packages in 600 attached a provenance asset to a release, and only one verified successfully. This is a striking result given that one half of our sample was deliberately drawn from among the most downloaded, most established packages in the PyPI ecosystem, exactly the population a security-conscious observer might expect provenance tooling to have reached first. It has not. We read this as evidence that, whatever security conversation is happening around MCP specifically, the broader software industry’s provenance story remains immature well beyond the MCP

ecosystem, and that framing provenance adoption as an MCP-specific gap to be closed risks missing the more general, more consequential gap.

6.3 The Composite Score Reversal: A Methodological Warning

The RQ5 finding we consider most important to the broader empirical software engineering community, independent of anything specific to MCP, is the SCH-score reversal documented in Section 4.4 and Section 6.5. Our naive, pipeline-computed composite score, which silently treated a failed Scorecard scan as equivalent to the worst possible Scorecard score, produced a statistically significant result *in the wrong direction*: it suggested MCP servers had better overall hygiene than baseline packages, a conclusion the complete-case analysis flatly contradicts ($p = 0.68$). The mechanism is now well understood given Section 6.1’s pipeline-attribution discussion: Group B failed Scorecard scanning at a higher rate than Group A (35.7% vs. 24.7%), driven by the same GitHub token permission limitation discussed in Section 6.1, and because the naive composite weights the Scorecard component most heavily (0.35 of the total), Group B’s higher Scorecard-stage attrition rate dragged its naive composite score down even though Group B’s *measured* security posture, where measurement succeeded, was if anything modestly better than Group A’s. A reader who trusted the naive composite score alone would have concluded the opposite of what the underlying, fully measured data supports.

We surface this not to criticize our own pipeline design in isolation, but because we believe the underlying pattern, composite risk scores silently treating missing measurements as worst-case measurements, is a structural risk in any tool, commercial or open-source, that aggregates multiple imperfectly-available signals (Scorecard, vulnerability scans, license detection, provenance checks) into a single number for prioritization or vendor comparison. A composite score’s blind spots are not random with respect to group membership when the underlying measurement infrastructure’s success rate is itself correlated with group membership, as ours was here. We recommend, as a concrete practice, that any tool computing a composite supply-chain risk score expose its underlying per-dimension measurement-success rate alongside the composite, and that consumers of such scores treat a composite computed across populations with differential measurement success as provisional until a complete-case or explicitly-imputed sensitivity check has been run.

6.4 Popularity Tracks Hygiene More Tightly in a Young Ecosystem

The stronger stars-to-hygiene correlation within Group A ($\rho = 0.50$) than within Group B ($\rho = 0.22$) admits at least two non-exclusive explanations, neither of which our cross-sectional data can adjudicate between. One possibility is a curation effect specific to a young, rapidly growing registry: in the absence of long track records, prospective users of an MCP server may rely more heavily on visible proxies like star count when deciding which server to adopt, which would tend to concentrate adoption on servers that also happen to look more carefully built, including on the hygiene dimensions we measure here, creating a tighter empirical coupling between popularity and hygiene than exists in a mature ecosystem like established PyPI packages, where popularity often reflects historical inertia accumulated over years largely independent of current hygiene practice. A second, harder-to-rule-out possibility is reverse or bidirectional causation operating over a short timescale unique to a new ecosystem: a server that happens to be built by a more security-conscious or more experienced team may both attract more attention through better documentation and presentation *and* independently exhibit better measured hygiene, with no causal arrow running through popularity itself. Distinguishing these explanations would require either longitudinal data tracking individual servers’ star growth against hygiene changes over time, or a controlled comparison of hygiene conditional on author experience, both of which we flag as natural extensions of this work in Section 8.

7 Threats to Validity

7.1 Internal Validity

The pipeline-attrition patterns documented in Section 6.1, particularly the GitHub token Branch-Protection permission limitation responsible for the majority of Scorecard failures, are a property of our specific scanning credentials and infrastructure rather than the scanned repositories, and we cannot fully rule out that this failure mode correlates with some unobserved repository property (for instance, organizations with stricter branch protection configurations might be systematically more likely to trigger the failing code path, which would bias our Scorecard sample toward less strictly governed repositories in a way not captured by our complete-case correction). The complete-case analysis in RQ5 addresses the consequence of this attrition for the composite score specifically but does not eliminate the possibility that our per-dimension Scorecard results in RQ2 are drawn from a subtly non-representative subset of each group’s full repository population.

7.2 External Validity

Our MCP server sample is a snapshot taken at a single point in time (pipeline run beginning 2026-06-29) of a protocol and registry ecosystem that is, by any measure, still in an early and fast-changing phase of its lifecycle; both the absolute hygiene figures reported here and, plausibly, the magnitude of the MCP-versus-baseline gaps we report should be expected to shift, likely toward improvement, as the ecosystem matures, as registry vetting improves, and as security tooling specifically targeting MCP servers becomes more widely adopted. Our baseline sample, drawn from top-download package rankings, is itself a sample of unusually *successful* general-purpose packages rather than a representative sample of the full npm/PyPI population; an unfiltered baseline sample would likely show worse hygiene on most dimensions, which would be expected to narrow, not widen, several of the gaps reported here. Findings should accordingly be read as a comparison between MCP servers and a relatively strong general-purpose baseline, not between MCP servers and “the average open-source package.”

7.3 Construct Validity

The ecosystem imbalance documented in Section 4.2 (Group A predominantly npm, Group B predominantly PyPI) is the most significant construct-validity threat in this study. We addressed it directly through ecosystem-stratified sensitivity analyses for every metric where the pooled sample size permitted a meaningful stratified test, and report that our headline RQ1 and RQ3 findings hold in direction and rough magnitude within both ecosystem strata considered separately. Our RQ2 finding is more sensitive to this threat: it is statistically significant within the PyPI stratum but not within the underpowered npm stratum, and we do not have a sufficiently large npm baseline sample in this study to confirm the aggregate Scorecard gap is not partly an npm-versus-PyPI ecosystem effect rather than purely an MCP-versus-baseline effect. Our vulnerability density metric, defined as raw known-vulnerability count divided by component count, also conflates exploitability-irrelevant and exploitability-critical vulnerabilities into a single figure; a VEX-style exploitability-aware density metric, which neither OSV.dev’s API nor our pipeline currently supports at scale, would be a more construct-valid measure of actual risk exposure, and we flag VEX adoption measurement as a natural follow-on study, particularly given the methodological precedent our own prior CycloneDX SBOM quality study establishes for this research direction [6].

7.4 Statistical Validity

We used Mann-Whitney U and Cliff’s δ throughout in light of the pronounced right-skew in nearly every continuous metric in this dataset, which we verified informally via the visual distributions in Figures 2 through 4 rather than through a formal normality test, since Mann-Whitney does not require a normality assumption to begin with and a formal test would not change our methodological choice. We did not

correct for multiple comparisons across the eighteen individual Scorecard checks reported in Table 3; at a Bonferroni-corrected threshold of $\alpha = 0.05/18 \approx 0.0028$, five of the seven checks we report as significant at $p < 0.01$ remain significant (Contributors, Code-Review, Vulnerabilities, CI-Tests, and Dependency-Update-Tool), while Packaging and Pinned-Dependencies would not survive correction; we flag this explicitly rather than silently applying the correction after the fact, since our primary claims rest on the three largest-effect checks, which survive any reasonable correction.

8 Conclusion and Future Work

This study set out to answer a narrow but, to our knowledge, previously unasked question: when measured by the same conventional software supply chain tooling applied to any other npm or PyPI package, how hygienic are published MCP servers? The answer is neither alarming nor reassuring in any simple sense. MCP servers carry meaningfully larger dependency trees and a measurably higher density of known vulnerabilities than a strong general-purpose baseline, differences that survive ecosystem-stratified sensitivity analysis and are unlikely to be fully explained away by the population’s youth alone. At the same time, much of the Scorecard-level gap we observe is explained by exactly the project-age and team-size factors a one-to-two-year-old protocol ecosystem would be expected to exhibit, and on the provenance dimension, MCP servers are not meaningfully worse than an established baseline because essentially no software in our sample, MCP or otherwise, has adopted SLSA provenance in any verifiable way. We conclude that the MCP security conversation, currently dominated by protocol-level concerns (authentication, prompt injection, tool poisoning), would benefit from explicitly incorporating the conventional supply-chain-hygiene lens this paper applies, not as a replacement for protocol-security research but as a complementary measurement axis that the existing literature has largely left unaddressed.

Beyond its substantive findings, this study also surfaces a methodological caution with relevance well outside the MCP context: composite supply-chain risk scores are only as trustworthy as the missing-data handling baked into their construction, and a naive implementation can silently reverse a paper’s, or a vendor tool’s, headline conclusion. We recommend complete-case reporting, or explicit, disclosed imputation, as a minimum methodological bar for any future work, including our own, that aggregates multiple imperfectly-measured supply-chain signals into a single score.

Three directions for future work follow directly from the limitations identified in Section 7. First, a longitudinal extension of this study, re-running the same pipeline against the same sampled servers at quarterly intervals, would allow the maturation hypothesis advanced in Section 6 to be tested directly rather than inferred from a single cross-sectional snapshot. Second, an exploitability-aware reanalysis using VEX statements, where available, or EPSS exploit-prediction scores in place of raw vulnerability counts would address the construct-validity limitation discussed in Section 7.3 and would directly extend the VEX-adoption measurement gap identified in prior OpenSSF survey work [15]. Third, a balanced-ecosystem replication, with deliberately matched npm and PyPI sample sizes in both groups, would close the one open question this study’s stratified sensitivity analysis could not fully resolve: whether the RQ2 Scorecard gap is a genuine MCP-versus-baseline effect or partly an artifact of the npm-versus-PyPI ecosystem composition difference between our two samples. We release our complete data collection pipeline, raw and processed datasets, and analysis code to support these and other extensions.

Data and Code Availability

The complete data collection pipeline (seven Python scripts covering sample construction, metadata collection, SBOM generation, Scorecard scanning, vulnerability lookup, provenance checking, and score computation), the resulting raw and merged datasets (600 packages \times 64 measured fields), all statistical analysis code, and the figure-generation scripts used to produce every figure in this paper are released as a companion artifact on Zenodo to support independent verification and reuse, following the same reproducibility practice established in our prior work [6]. The full 600-row dataset is provided in

machine-readable CSV form in that artifact; Appendix A reproduces a representative 25-row excerpt for inspection within this document.

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A Dataset Excerpt

Table 4 reproduces a 25-row stratified excerpt of the full 600-row master dataset for inspection within this document; `sch_score` here is the pipeline’s naive (uncorrected) composite score as defined in Section 4.3, included for continuity with the released raw dataset. The complete dataset, including all 64 measured fields per package and the corrected complete-case scores discussed in Section 4.4, is available in the companion Zenodo artifact referenced in the Data and Code Availability statement.

Table 4: Representative 25-row excerpt of the master dataset.

Package	Eco.	Grp	Stars	Comp.	Score	VulnDens.	SCH
io.github.bytedance/mcp-server-browser	npm	A	37,389	7731		0.040	0.494
io.github.anyproto/anytype-mcp	npm	A	461	134	6.3	0.017	0.772
bear-notes-mcp	npm	A	201	483	4.4	0.087	0.679
io.github.satelliteoflove/godot-mcp	npm	A	113	107	4.4	0.387	0.628
io.github.Mearman/mcp-wayback-machine	npm	A	35	634	4.4	0.043	0.688
io.github.pinchwork/pinchwork	pypi	A	11	202		0.746	0.381
io.github.adelpro/quran-search-engi...	npm	A	5	101	1.6	0.330	0.519
io.github.aeoess/agent-passport-mcp	npm	A	2	111	4.5	0.019	0.687
io.github.airblackbox/air-blackbox-mcp	pypi	A	1	0	2.7	0.000	0.420
io.github.varvararatta/country_dat...	unknown	A	0	0	2.2	0.000	0.397
@ranki.io/cli	npm	A	0	94	1.6	0.054	0.561
com.dyndns-server.noon-ai/automatic...	unknown	A		0		0.000	0.300
langchain-groq	pypi	B	140,502	2440	5.9	0.007	0.755
pipreqs	pypi	B	7,453	95	3.8	0.360	0.608
itsdangerous	pypi	B	3,123	90	5.6	0.449	0.820
django-hosts	pypi	B	1,057	12		0.000	0.450
mypy-boto3-simplifiedv2	pypi	B	672	165	3.9	0.578	0.564
sagemaker-inference	pypi	B	413	0	4.2	0.000	0.486
linkedin-api-client	pypi	B	259	65		1.220	0.311
tbump	pypi	B	172	40		0.061	0.476
scroll-to	npm	B	85	0	2.6	0.000	0.415
poppler-utils	pypi	B	43	9	3.2	0.000	0.597
cheap-repr	pypi	B	26	4	3.1	0.000	0.587
zi-api-auth-client	pypi	B	10	0	4.0	0.000	0.477
colcon-output	pypi	B	3	2	3.6	0.000	0.559

B Pipeline Failure Taxonomy

Table 5 summarizes the dominant failure reasons recorded at each pipeline stage, referenced throughout Section 5 and Section 6.

Table 5: Dominant failure reasons by pipeline stage, both groups combined.

Stage	Failure reason	Count
Scorecard	GitHub token cannot read branch protection rules	110
Scorecard	Empty/unparseable Scorecard response	39
Scorecard	Scan timeout (300s)	21
SBOM (Syft)	Git clone timeout (120s)	5
SBOM (Syft)	Repository not found / authentication required	13
Vulnerability lookup	No SBOM available (cascaded from SBOM stage)	41
Vulnerability lookup	OSV.dev batch query network failure	14
Provenance check	No GitHub Release published (informative, not an error)	211
Provenance check	Genuine network/connection failure	9